

MODERN APPROACHES AND INNOVATIONS IN LEARNING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY GRADES

Abdurahmanova Muhabbat Rakhimjanovna

Namangan region, Yangikurgan district,

English teacher of the 11th school

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898315>

Abstract: In this article, as a result of the use of modern approaches and innovative methods in teaching English in elementary grades, the development of students' logical thinking skills, fluency in speech, the formation of quick and correct answer skills, and the development of enthusiasm for knowledge, information is given about the effort to prepare thoroughly for classes.

Keywords: modern, innovation, elementary, game, educational, education

the most fundamental and positive changes in modern primary education is the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" " is Resolution No. PQ-1875. On the basis of this decision, learning foreign languages, mainly English, from the 1st grade of general secondary schools in the form of game-style lessons and oral speech lessons, and from the 2nd grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar teaching begins step by step. According to the decision, under the leadership of the Coordinating Council, which is constantly working on the further development of the study of foreign languages, an incomparable scale of work was started in all directions of the educational field. For example, since the 2013-2014 school year, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of game-style exercises and oral speech lessons has been started in the first grades of secondary schools. Also, textbooks and teaching-methodical sets for these classes were created. It is worth noting that the games in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the children. Children began their first acquaintance with a foreign language by learning the culture of greetings, colors and everyday words in the form of a dialogue.

Undoubtedly, equipping the foreign language rooms in the educational institutions of our country with modern information and communication technologies and advanced technical means of teaching, broadcasting programs and broadcasts on TV and radio channels that teach children and teenagers foreign languages, the history of other countries and Regular screening of popular foreign art and multimedia films dedicated to culture, world science and technical news with Uzbek subtitles allowed our young people to get to know the past, culture and science of the peoples of the world.

When teaching foreign languages to students in primary grades, especially in the first grade, it is necessary to take into account the age, physiological and psychological characteristics of the student. As noted in the decision, the implementation of foreign language teaching in the form of game-style lessons and oral speech lessons in the first grades is really suitable for younger students. The use of game technologies in education is one of the most effective tools. During the game, their thinking, outlook, and thinking will expand. Scientists believe that the game approach to education facilitates the learning process. It not only makes it easier, but also increases the interest in this subject and encourages the child to acquire deep knowledge. Game-style lessons help children develop their oral language. First graders really like different visuals with pictures or videos. Games should be regularly used to develop their

speech through different colored pictures. For example, What is this ?, Who is this?, Who knows the most words? games like During the game, it is necessary to encourage children to remember words and pronounce them correctly . Depending on the growth of children's vocabulary, it is important to organize other types of games and various competitions. At first, children can perform exercises on topics such as "Fruit Names", "Occupations", "Home Appliances" with the help of games. Then, if they are shown in a harmonious state to the colorful images on the computer , the pupils' speech will develop and the circle of attitude to the environment will expand. During the presentation phase of the new topic, words and pictures will appear on the screen. Students will be able to listen to the words and pronounce them. It is necessary to pay attention to the principle of individualization of education when presenting the subject with the help of a computer. Some students find it difficult to accept the graphic image of the word, and some have difficulty with the sound image. The computer solves this or that difficulty by means of exercises, helps to find the aspects of the student who have difficulty in mastering the English language and to eliminate them.

Starting from the second grade, other educational games aimed at mastering grammar can be organized. For example, "Who is literate?" , Who is clever?, "Who am I?", "Chain", "Role game", "Find the place of the word" are among these interesting games. "Who's smart? " game gives a good result in improving spelling literacy. In this case, 5-6 words are written on cardboard, and the words are written correctly and incorrectly. Students are required to find the misspelled word and write it correctly . The winner of the game is determined by which student is the first to correctly write the misspelled words .

We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach independent thinking. Today, English language teachers, relying on the experience of pedagogues from the United States of America and England, use the following innovative methods:

"Merry riddles" (Merry riddles) teaching riddles to students. It is important to teach English, they learn unfamiliar words and find answers to riddles . " Quick answers" help to improve the effectiveness of the lesson . Chigil wrote" (Warm-up exercises) using various games in the classroom to make students interested in the lesson. "Pantomime" (Pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are done and the students are tired. "A chain story" method helps to improve students' oral speech and strengthen memory. "Acting characters" method can be used in all types of lessons. "When pictures speak" method is more convenient and in teaching English It helps in the development of zaki speech, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic. Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time.

"Find the place of the word " game, the places of the words are changed and a sentence is formed by putting the words in their place. The game "Collection" is held in order to strengthen the acquired knowledge of students based on a certain topic. The game is organized in the form of a row competition or work in small groups. For example, groups are given a task to find words that represent a symbol. The group that finds the most in the given time is the winner. Cartoons. While learning a foreign language, children do not understand the words in the cartoon, but they try to understand the words they use through the actions of

the characters in the cartoon. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language. Children are taught English through songs, poems , stories, and videos.

"Picture" game. A picture game can be used for students to better master the content of Present Continuous. Readers are invited to find what the character in the pictures they have not seen is doing. For example, P1: Is the girl sitting at the table? P 2 : No, she is not.

P1: Is the girl standing? P 2 :: Yes, she is

correctly guesses the movement represented in the picture is considered the winner. He takes another picture as a starter.

" Sentences in the picture" game . This game is a good visual tool for practicing grammar forms. There are several pictures on the cards that represent some kind of human action, for example: there are pictures of skating, playing chess, reading a book. The teacher shows picture cards (the boy is skating) and asks: What is he doing? Students find the same picture and answer: He is skating.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in teaching English, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, the interest in learning a foreign language, the preparation of modern didactic developments based on pedagogical technologies that help to fully satisfy the need. and developing a robust mechanism for their implementation provides a practical solution to the problem.

References:

1. Decision PQ-1875 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages " .
2. Iriskulov AT and others Kids' English pupil's book 2nd class - Tashkent - Uzbekistan; 2014
3. Passov Ye.I. Communicative method obuchenia inoyazichnomu govoreniyu. M.: Prosve shch enie , 1991
4. Hoshimov O'. Yakubov I. Methodology of teaching English. T., - 2003
5. Vyatyutnev MN Obuchenie inostrannomu yaziku v nachalnoy shkole. / foreign language and school, 1990